

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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Integrated Platform Design and Development v2 and Platform Validation v1

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market & Trends Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D4.3 titled as “Integrated Platform Design and Development-v2 and Platform Validation-v1” refers to the first complete version of the integrated ToyLabs platform, including the description of the platform, while it also provides updates to the integration plan presented in D4.2, defining the steps for the next versions of the platform till the final fully integrated version.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the developed software, the source code of which can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

D4.3 will be updated on the basis of the pilot validation results and the comments received by the pilot users, leading to the final version of the integrated platform at the end of the development circle, resulting to deliverable D4.4 and to the release of the stable final version of the Collaboration Platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D4.3 titled as “Integrated Platform Design and Development-v2 and Platform Validation-v1” refers to the first complete version of the integrated Toylabs Platform. The present document includes the description of the platform and of the fully integrated versions of the components. In addition, it provides the first results of Task 4.3 – Toylabs Platform Verification and Validation, including the definition of the approach to follow for the validation of the platform.

The deliverable is of “Demonstrator” type, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the actual software platform developed and released. The source code and the relevant documentation can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D4.3 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the first complete/ integrated version of the Toylabs Platform and details regarding each individual added value component included.
- Section 4 describes the approach decided and followed in the framework of the project for the validation of the platform and its components.
- Section 5 concludes the deliverable, stating what is expected till the end of the project in the framework of WP4

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

Deliverable D4.3 gets input from the deliverables of WP3 including the descriptions of the added value components of the platform. D4.3 uses the previous deliverable of WP4 (D4.2) as a basis and updates it as far it concerns the components which have been developed and integrated to the platform. In addition, it includes the first results of T4.3, defining the validation approach to follow. As the software platform further evolves, mainly on the basis of the feedback received by the pilot users, D4.3 will serve as the intermediary point of D4.2 and D4.4.

2 Toylabs Integrated Platform

2.1 Core Platform

Since the previous release of the platform and the deliverable D4.2, no update has taken place in the architecture of the Core Platform, while the integration of all the components has been completed.

In the present release of the platform, the components have all achieved UI-Level integration, allowing the user to seamlessly move from the Core Platform to the rest of the components and back, without becoming obvious whether the components are autonomous or part of a monolithic solution.

This stands not only for the Partner Matching and Negotiation and the Market & Trend Analysis components, as initially planned (see D4.1 and D4.2), but also for the Augmented Reality Feedback component which was supposed to achieve only API-Level integration in the present release. However, the development of the component has been accelerated in order to have everything ready by Month 15, so UI-Level integration has been already achieved.

From the perspective of the end user the only updates to the platform to be implemented, till the end of the project, refer to fixing any bugs reported during the piloting phase and to making minor improvements in order to further enhance user experience.

From the perspective of the administrators, the Admin panel will be further developed, towards the direction of delivering a final version which will include tools for automating usual complex administration processes, thus reducing the effort for managing the platform. Details on the new features and tool to be added will be provided in D4.4.

2.2 Integrated Components

2.2.1 Market Trends Analysis component

2.2.1.1 Description

This component is intended to give the user an easy-to-use tool that will provide him with the appropriate information - through various, intuitive charts- to help him on the one hand identify market trends for his domain of interest and on the other hand gain a deeper understanding of customers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction on specific topics (either products/toys or brands) and as a result on their brand perception, campaign efficiency and competitors' position in the market.

The component works by harvesting data from social media and other online sources where people express their opinions and have discussions on products/ brands etc. The user that initiates the analysis is responsible for setting the keywords, hashtags, phrases and accounts that will be used for gathering the data. The user is then able to either perform a trend analysis to uncover popular trends in a given domain or collect and analyse customers' feedback as expressed in the web.

The development of said component is now complete as well as its integration in ToyLabs Collaboration Platform. During the next months, the component, along with the entire platform, will be tested in real life scenarios via two pilot cases and the feedback gathered during this stage will be used to improve it.

2.2.1.2 Architecture

The Market and Trend Analysis component consists of three main, distinct parts; the User Interface, the Communication Layer and the Natural Language Processing and Analytics engine. Figure 1 depicts the component's high level architecture, namely these three layers along with their internal structure.

The User Interface is responsible for providing the user with insights into the collected data, while guiding him to apply filters, make intuitive queries and browse the results through advanced visualisations. The basic technologies used for this layer are PHP and JavaScript.

The Communication layer manages and directs the flow of data between the two other layers, namely the component's User Interface and the Analytics engine. The Python Django REST framework will be used for this purpose, in conjunction with a TCP module that will handle the authorisation and the communication between the UI and the Python portion of the analytics engine.

Figure 1: Architecture of Market and Trends Analysis Component

Finally, the Natural language processing and analytics engine is responsible for the data retrieval, data processing and the implementation of all required computations to perform emotion analysis and identify trending topics. The basic technologies that are used are the “Elasticsearch” engine, the “Couchbase server” database, the “NLTK” framework and the “Scikit learn” library.

2.2.1.3 Integration

The Market and Trend Analysis component was integrated in the ToyLabs Core Platform by expanding the platform’s user interface and connecting the engine to the backend. As seen in Figure 1, the integration took place in the platform’s middle application logic layer through a list of API calls that request specific information from the module. The module’s frontend has been integrated, as already stated, using JavaScript and the libraries D3 and AMCHARTS. It is based on the built-in modules of VueJS to communicate with a RESTful API. The module stores its data in a separate database than that of the core platform. Finally, the user initialises the module in the product development’s Research phase, which is the second phase after concept definition, and prompts the user to start either a Market Trends or a Social Feedback analysis.

Concerning the component’s API calls there are six endpoints that make API calls; accounts, analyses, concepts, parameters, projects and retrievers. Moreover,

there are five basic API calls that every endpoint can perform; list, create, read, update and delete that are self-explanatory. However, it should be mentioned that a user will only be able to perform the calls list and read in the accounts endpoint, because this is referring to the social media accounts that the user specifies to harvest data from. As such, a user of the ToyLabs platform cannot create, update or delete a social media account of a different individual/organisation. The other endpoints have to do with the tasks that the Market Trends Analysis component performs and as such can be read, listed, created, updated and deleted by the user.

To summarise, three of the endpoints (concepts, parameters, retrievers) can only perform the abovementioned five basic API calls and the endpoint accounts the API class list and read. For the endpoint named projects, those five API calls may be performed as well as two additional named analyses and concepts that ask for the analyses and concepts tied with said project.

Finally, the analyses endpoint may perform eight additional API calls that will be listed and explained below:

- **get_concept_timelines**: Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the concepts used in the analysis.

- **get_parameter_facets**: For the given parameter get number of results for each of the (**concept**, **parameter** value) pairs per concept. A query parameter named "parameter" is expected, with value the parameter id.

- **get_overall_timeline**: Daily number of documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.

- **parameters**: Get the list of parameters that are available in the analysis. The "**is_enabled**" field defines whether each of them will be used to create a separate chart.

- **get_timelines**: Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the **keyphrases_settings** defined in the analysis. Only **keyphrases_settings** of types 0 and 1 are shown.

- **get_top_accounts**: Get the 10 most active accounts (based on the number of documents published by them) from the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.

- **get_top_hashtags**: Get the 10 most popular hashtags from the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.

- **get_two_word_phrases**: Get the 15 most commonly found two-word phrases in the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings per concept.

In the following part some indicative screenshots of the Market Trends Analysis tool will be presented:

Figure 2: MT Tool Custom Settings

Figure 3: MT Tool Time Settings

Market Trend Analysis

[← Back to Market Analysis](#)

Custom Settings Time Settings **Concepts' Settings**

Provide specific meaningful **concepts of interest** (e.g. baby dolls) and **parameters** (e.g. colour, material) that will be presented and formulate the visualisations accordingly in order to be provided with useful and meaningful information customized to your needs.

The **concepts of interest** are terms/ideas that you want to monitor and understand crowd perception and market trends spinning around these terms. The value format follows the same logic as the keywords in the Custom Settings tab.

The **parameters** you need to specify are features on which the concepts of interest will be analysed and compared (e.g. a baby doll made of wood or plastic. The parameter name here is the "material" and the values "wood, plastic"). The value format is comma separated values.

Concepts

Name	Values	Actions
Concept 1	<input type="text" value="puzzle games mac"/>	
Concept 2	<input type="text" value="physics games physic game"/>	
Concept 3	<input type="text" value="toy story"/>	
		Add Concept

Figure 4: MT Tool Concept Settings (1/2)

Concepts

Name	Values	Actions
Concept 1	<input type="text" value="puzzle games mac"/>	
Concept 2	<input type="text" value="physics games physic game"/>	
Concept 3	<input type="text" value="toy story"/>	
		Add Concept

Parameters

Name	Values	Enabled	Actions
material	colour, wood, metal		
			Add Parameter

Save as copy Update

Figure 5: MT Tool Concept Settings (2/2)

Overview

Settings-based analytics

Figure 6: MT Tool Visualisations (1/2)

Figure 7: MT Tool Visualisations (2/2)

2.2.2 Partner Matching and Negotiation component

2.2.2.1 Description

The Partner Matching & Negotiation (PMN) component is a tool that can be used by users to inquire about collaborators, inside the Toylabs Platform, allowing them to set up formal partnerships, that will lead to collaborative design and development of products.

In more detail, the PMN component is responsible for handling a handful of operations that range from partner searching to matchmaking between different platform users, enabling specific collaboration opportunities.

2.2.2.2 Architecture

Partner Matching and Negotiation component is an infrastructure that relies on a three-tier architecture. A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the following figure.

Figure 8: PMN High Level Architecture

2.2.2.3 Integration

The PMN component has the highest level of integration, including direct access to the core platform's database, thus, for the end user can be considered as an actual part of the core platform. It allows the user to:

- Search for collaborators,

- Find a collaborator through a parametrized search, or directly using its name,
- Negotiate the terms of a collaboration,
- Exchange files and contracts,
- Form a collaboration, and
- Provide limited access to private product information

Indicative screenshots of the component, are presented next.

Figure 9: Initiating a collaboration

Collaborations

Design: Design A

[← Back to Designs](#)

Overview **Search**

ADVANCED SEARCH

I am looking for a: Toy Manufacturer FabLab Child Expert Safety Expert

That has any the following competencies:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Clear
Search

Search results

1. Singular Logic

✔ Toy Manufacturer

ISO9001

SingularLogic is the No 1 Greek Software Vendor and one of the largest Integrated IT Solutions Group in Greece. Its activities comprise of the development and distribution of business software applications, design and implementation of Integrated IT Solutions for large enterprises of the private and public sector, including distribution and support of well-established international IT products. SingularLogic, member of Marfin Investment Group, has highly skilled personnel, specialized know ...

✔ 3D Modelling
✘ Vacuum Forming

Contact
Add

Figure 10: Searching for a collaboration through criteria matching

Collaborations

Design: Design A

[← Back to Designs](#)

Overview **Search**

Singular Logic
✔ Toy Manufacturer

That has any the following competencies:

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Clear
Search

Figure 11: Searching by name

Figure 12: Negotiating the terms of collaboration and exchange of files and contracts

Figure 13: List of Collaborations

Due to the delicate nature of IPR, only the Manager (Owner) of the organisation can add a collaborator to a product, regardless of who took part in the negotiations.

2.2.3 Augmented Reality Feedback component

2.2.3.1 Description

The Augmented Reality Feedback Component (ARF Component or ARFC) is a tool used to present 3D models to users (both professionals and end-users), and to allow them to interact with toys early in the production cycle. This gives the manufacturers the advantage to get feedback and improve their product designs, saving them both money and time.

The ARFC consists of 3 different sub-modules: Augmented Reality system for model presentation and interaction, Voting and Feedback system for obtaining feedback from user, and Feedback Evaluation system, used by product owners for evaluating the results, so they can enhance their product designs.

2.2.3.2 Architecture

At the time the present deliverable is being compiled, the Augmented Reality Feedback is fully integrated in the Toylabs platform, in respect to the integration plan provided in D4.2.

The following figure represents the architecture of the component, showing in a clear way both the different screens as part of ARF user interface and the connectors to the core platform at application logic layer.

Figure 14: ARF High Level Architecture

2.2.3.3 Integration

The Augmented Reality Feedback component, due to the need for a mobile application, has a more complex integration (as can be seen from architecture in Figure 14) than other components.

In the ToyLabs Core Platform there's the sub-module that allows product owners to upload Augmented Reality (AR) models, to define questions for the AR app users and to view and analyze the feedback of those users. The integration took place in the platform's middle application logic layer through a list of (internal) API calls that request and save specific information to the sub-module. The sub-module's frontend is based on the build-in modules of VueJS. Finally, the user can initialize the module from any Design or Prototype he (or his organization) owns, thus making it available in both the Design and the Prototype phases.

To compliment the integration with the platform, an iOS application is provided. The application communicates with the platform to get access to AR models and submit feedback to the product owner, through a RESTful API:

- `login`: Used to *post* user's email and password to the platform to login and obtain a token to sign all other requests and identify the user.
- `user`: Used to *get* user information (name, avatar, organizations, etc)
- `ar-models`: Used to *get* a list of all AR models the user has access to. This includes user's own models, user organizations' models and models that belong to designs and prototypes the user (or his organization) is working (collaborating) on.
- `ar-model/{id}/download`: *Gets* the information for a specific AR model.
- `ar-model/{id}/questions`: Used to *get* a list of questions to be presented to the user after using the AR model, for providing feedback to the product owner.
- `ar-model/{id}/feedback`: Used to *post* user's feedback to the backend. Feedback includes both answer to the questions (from a scale 1

to 5), and free text comments.

- `file/{id}`: Downloads model files for a specific AR model.

Next, you can see a list of indicative screenshots from the Augmented Reality Feedback Component, from both the iOS and the Platform point of view:

The screenshot shows a web dashboard for 'TOYLABS'. The navigation bar includes 'Dashboard', 'Members', and 'About'. On the right, there are icons for email, notifications, and a user profile for 'Marios Finik'. The main content area is titled 'Product Prototypes' and features a 'Back to Dashboard' button. Below this is a table with columns for 'Title', 'Last Modified', and 'AR Models'. The table lists two prototypes: 'Test Production Prototype' and 'Lorem Ipsum', both modified '1 day ago'. The 'AR Models' column contains icons for editing, viewing, commenting, deleting, and liking. A blue '+ Add Prototype' button is located at the bottom right of the table.

Title	Last Modified	AR Models
Test Production Prototype	1 day ago	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lorem Ipsum	1 day ago	

Figure 15: Initiating ARFC

Create AR Model

[← Back to AR Models](#)

Title

Description

Use this field to explain to users:

- what to expect,
- how to use the model,
- possible shortcomings,
- what to test,
- whatever you think is necessary to know before they use the model.

Files

For the model to work correctly, all the nodes of the 3D model should be under a parent node and that parent node should have the exact same name as the filename of the model. Keep in mind that, when opened in the ToyLabs app, the front of the model will be displayed, so make sure it is designed accordingly. **Supported file types:** fbx, obj, 3ds, stl, dae, stl (and image files for use as textures).

Drop files here to upload

Questions

Users that download your AR model will be asked to rate it based on a number of criteria (change to suit your specific needs). Rating will be done using a scale of 1-5.

Question 1	Design
Question 2	Features
Question 3	Novelty

Figure 16: Creating AR Model

Figure 17: List of Toys/AR Models

Figure 18: AR Model Preview

Figure 19: Feedback Evaluation System

3 Platform Validation Approach

The essential parts of software validation are the quality model, the method of evaluation, software measurement, and the supporting tools. To develop good software, quality requirements should be specified, the software quality assurance process should be planned, implemented and controlled, and both intermediate products and end products should be evaluated.

ToyLabs evaluation activities will use as reference the Software Product Quality Evaluation Reference Model that describes the process, activities and tasks performed during the quality evaluation of a software product. This reference model is defined by the standard ISO/IEC 25040 that contains general requirements for specification and evaluation of software quality and clarifies the general concepts providing a process description for evaluating quality of software product stating the requirements for the application of the evaluation process.

Functional evaluation criteria modules provide a flexible and structured approach to define criteria for monitoring the quality of intermediate products during the development process and for evaluation of final products. The purpose of using evaluation modules is to ensure that software evaluations can be repeatable, reproducible and objective. These modules define a set of structured instructions and data used for an evaluation. It specifies the criteria applicable to evaluate a quality characteristic and it identifies the evidence it needs. It also defines the elementary evaluation procedure and the format for reporting the measurements resulting from the application of the technique.

The evaluation modules define the criteria for the evaluation of the ToyLabs components considering the functional characteristics.

In a software development project, use cases define system software requirements. Use case development begins early on, so real use cases for key product functionality are available in early iterations. Use cases tell the customer what to expect, the developer what to code, the technical writer what to document, and the tester what to test. For software testing -- which consists of many interrelated tasks, each with its own artefacts and deliverables -- creation of test cases is the first fundamental step. Then test procedures are designed for these test cases, and finally, test scripts are created to implement the procedures. Test cases are a key to the process because they identify and communicate the conditions that will be implemented in test and are necessary to verify successful and acceptable implementation of the product requirements. They are all about making sure that the product fulfils the requirements of the system.

A test case is a set of test inputs, execution conditions, and expected results developed for a particular objective: to exercise a particular program path or verify

compliance with a specific requirement, for implemented in test. Test cases are necessary to verify successful and acceptable implementation of the product requirements. The evaluation team proposed to use a three-step process for generating ToyLabs test cases. For each ToyLabs use case a full set of use-case scenarios have already been generated in the context of D1.2. These scenarios, were later used to define the platform’s requirements depending on the type of user, the specific module being used as well as the phase of the toy development process.

The template of the test case is reported below. The test case template includes a test case ID and the test scenario description. The ID is a simple incremental number to make the test case easy to identify and it is unique. The scenario is the textual description of the test case objective.

The main part of the test case is correlated to the steps; for each line:

- Step ID: provides the incremental step identifier (independently from the test case ID)
- Test Step: provides the information for the tester about what to do
- Test Data: data to insert when applicable
- Expected Results: the result that the system should return having as input the action and the test data. Result can be a number, a behaviour, a state or even an error
- Actual Result: evaluation of results
 - o Yes: the result is the one expected
 - o Partial: there are troubles but the user can progress anyway in the process
 - o No: the result is wrong or the user is not able to progress

Test Case TU01 ID				
Test Case Scenario	Log in the platform			
Step ID	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results
ID01	1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 2. Enter username and password	User's credentials	User successfully logins to the platform	Yes Partial No

Figure 15: Test case Template and Example

Results are summarized in the following table as follows:

- Test Case ID: same as test case
- Test Scenario: same as test case
- Test Data: summary of data in the test case
- Expected results: result of the overall test case
- Actual result: actual result of the overall test case
- Pass/Fail: evaluation of the overall test case following rules in chapter 4.2.3

In the following matrixes the test cases are created from the High-level usage case scenarios and the generalised requirements generated in the context of D1.2 along with the current knowledge of the platform's functionality. The actual results and the pass/fail columns will be filled in the next version of the present deliverable.

ToyLabs Collaboration Platform						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	User registration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 2. Click on the Register button 3. Enter required information correctly 4. Press "Register" button 	Username E-mail Password x2	Successful registration if user enter information correctly Unsuccessful registration if user failed to enter required information correctly		
ID02	Log in/ Log out	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 	Username Password OR Facebook account	Successful Log in if user enter information correctly Unsuccessful Log in if user		

		<p>2. Click on the Log In button</p> <p>3. Enter required information correctly</p> <p>4. Press "Log In" button</p> <p>5. Press "Log Out" button to log out</p>	OR Google+ account	<p>failed to enter required information correctly</p> <p>Successful Log out in every case</p>		
ID03	Edit profile	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/profile/edit</p> <p>2. Edit personal information</p> <p>3. Join or create an organisation</p> <p>4. Click on the "Update" button</p>	Various personal information	<p>Successful update of personal information by clicking the "Update" button</p> <p>Cancellation of all changed information by pressing the "Cancel" button</p>		
ID04	Members	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/organizations</p> <p>2. View a list of all registered organisations in the platform</p>	-	Successful loading of the organisations page		
ID05	Public projects	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu</p> <p>2. Click on any public project</p> <p>3. View information/ images</p>	-	Successful loading of public projects, ability to like and comment		

		about project 4. Like and comment				
ID06	Dashboard	1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/dashboard 2. View a list of all ongoing projects 3. Create a new project by clicking on the “New product” button 4. View personal messages and notifications 5. Search for a project	-	Successful loading of dashboard and all of its functionalities		
ID07	Rating System	1. Click on a collaborator profile 2. Rate said collaborator	-	Successful rating of organisation		
ID08	Project Creation	1. Click on the “New Product” button 2. Enter title and description 3. Choose the product category 4. Choose the age groups 5. Choose the legal owner of the product 6. Choose if the product	Product general information, images, files	Successful creation of new product		

		will be public 7. Add Images and Files 8. Press the "Create" button				
ID09	Design	1. Click on the "Design" tab 2. Click on the "Add Design" button 3. Enter title, description and choose if the design will be public 4. Add images and files 5. Press the "Create" button	Design general information, images, files	Successful creation of new design		
ID10	Edit design	1. Click on the "Edit Design" button 2. Update information 3. Click on the "Update" button				
ID11	Create new design version	1. Click on the "Create New Version" button 2. Click Yes when prompted 3. Old design is archived		Successful creation of new version and archiving of old		
ID12	Create new prototype	1. Click on the	Prototype information,			

		<p>“Prototype” tab</p> <p>2. Click on the “Add Prototype” button</p> <p>3. Enter title, description and choose if the prototype will be public</p> <p>4. Add images and files</p> <p>5. Press the “Create” button</p>	images and files			
ID10	Edit Prototype	<p>1. Click on the “Edit Prototype” button</p> <p>2. Update information</p> <p>3. Click on the “Update” button</p>				
ID11	Move prototype to production	<p>1. Click on the “Move to Production” button</p> <p>2. Product is ready to be produced</p>	Working prototype			

Table 4-1: TCP Test Cases

ToyLabs Market Trends Analysis Module						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/</p>	-	Successful initialization of Market Trends module		

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Click on the Register button Choose between Market Trends or Social Feedback Analysis 				
ID02	Custom settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Click the Custom Settings tab Name the analysis Enter keywords to be used as search terms Select social media channels Enable/disable influencers mode 	<p>Analysis name</p> <p>Words, phrases, hashtags to be used as search terms</p>	Successful loading of custom settings page. Ability to modify the custom settings		
ID03	Time settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Click the Time Settings tab Enter from and to dates Alternatively click the “Last week”, “Last month” or “Last year” buttons 	Time period for data harvesting	<p>Successful loading of time settings</p> <p>Successful setting of from and to dates when pressing the “Last week”, “Last month” or “Last year” buttons</p>		
ID04	Concept’s settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Click the Concept’s Settings tab Add concepts and values for them Add parameters 	Concepts, parameters that will formulate the visualisations	<p>Successful loading of Concept’s Settings</p> <p>Correct visualisations according to concepts and</p>		

		and value for them		parameters defined		
ID05	Create analysis	1. Click the Create button	-	Successful creation of analysis		
ID06	Edit analysis	1. Click the "Edit Analysis" button 2. Modify analysis 3. Save as copy or update	-	Successful update of analysis		
ID07	See visualized analytics	1. Click the "View Analysis" button 2. View visualised analytics	-	Successful loading of visualisations according to the user's settings		

Table 4-2: MT Module Test Cases

ToyLabs Partner Matching Module						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	1. Navigate to Design or Prototype stage 2. Click on the Collaborations button next to a design or prototype 3. See an overview of all discussions or search for a new partner	-	Successful initialization of Market Trends module		
ID02	Search for partner	1. Click the Search tab 2. Search by name	Partner name or information	Successful loading of all suitable partners		

		<p>Or</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Use advanced search 4. Choose type of partner, competencies, scale of production needed, payment method and time 5. Click the "Search" button 	to search for one			
ID03	Overview	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Overview" tab 2. Invite a partner to a step of the process 3. Select suitable partners 4. Accept or decline responses 		Successful handling of all partner matching related tasks		

Table 4-3: PM Module Test Cases

ToyLabs Augmented Reality Module						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to Design or Prototype stage 2. Click on the "AR Models" button next to a design or prototype 	-	Successful initialization of Augmented Reality module		

		3. See an overview of all AR models or add a new one				
ID02	Add AR model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the "Add AR Model" tab 2. Enter title and description 3. Add files of the correct format 4. Choose the criteria that users will be asked to rate when downloading the AR model 5. Click on the "Create" button 	AR model information, images and files	Successful creation of AR model		
ID03	Overview	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "AR Models" button next to a design or prototype 2. See an overview of all AR models 3. View number of downloads, Comments and mean rating 4. Accept or decline responses 	-	Successful viewing of all AR models and relevant information		
ID04	Edit AR model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Edit AR Model" button next 	-	Successful update of AR model		

		to an AR model 2. Modify information and files 3. Click on the "Update" button				
ID05	Delete AR model	1. Click on the "Delete AR Model" button next to an AR model 2. Click Yes when prompted	-	Successful deletion of AR model		

Table 3-1: AR Module Test Cases

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D4.3 accompanies the 2nd release of the Toylabs Integrated Platform. It has provided an update of the different components of the platform which has been fully integrated in order to provide a uniform experience to the end user. The integrated platform is ready in order to be validated in full extend by the pilots of the project. The deliverable also provided a detailed description of the approach to be used in the framework of the project for the validation of all the components and of the integrated platform.

4.2 Next Steps

The next steps include the validation of the integrated platform through its pilot application, as the platform is ready to be used in practice by all types of users. Till the end of the project the development team will collect any bugs found, comments or ideas for improvement and after prioritizing them will proceed in relevant updates either of the core platform or of specific components.

In addition, some helpful tools will be developed and added in order to automate tasks in the administration of the platform. These tools will refer only to the Toylabs platform administrators, without any involvement of the end-users and without affecting their experience.

A final version of the integrated platform including all the updates that will be considered as important will be delivered on Month 18 of the project.

As far as it concerns the validation of the platform, the approach described in Section 3 will be further elaborated and applied in the final version of the integrated platform. The respective results will be included in D4.4 'ToyLabs Integrated Platform Design, Development and Validation- final version.